
Monte Carlo Propagation for Confidence Scoring of Ventricular Tachycardia Ablation Targets in Patient-Specific Cardiac Models

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Abstract

Ventricular tachycardia (VT) occurs when scarred myocardial tissue creates self-sustaining reentrant circuits disrupting normal ventricular rhythm. Catheter ablation treats VT by focusing on critical circuit sites, or ablation targets. However, the models used in clinical spaces are deterministic—relying on singular simulation runs that can overlook critical ablation sites and lead to increased procedural costs or other potential complications. This study applied Monte Carlo Propagation (MCP) to a clinically-standard Eikonal Cardiac Model to quantify uncertainty in ablation target prediction. A computational pipeline processed data from the Evaluation of Myocardial Infarction from Delayed-Enhancement Cardiac MRI (EMIDEC) dataset: MRI scans were segmented, then converted into meshes using GMSH, reformatted into FEniCS format for finite element analysis, and used for electrophysiological simulation. The uncertainty framework then identified targets that were stable across various parameters and assigned confidence scores for decision support. Across nine patients, the MCP model achieved 33.7% target stability, with 21.0 stable nodes per case. Compared to its deterministic counterpart, MCP was able to improve top-10 precision by 40.0 percentage points (0.967 MCP vs. 0.567 deterministic) and was able to flag 36.8% of the deterministic predictions as low-confidence false positives. In terms of Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC), MCP had an AUC (area under the curve) of 0.966 while the deterministic baseline had an AUC of 0.500, demonstrating the model’s ability to differentiate high and low confidence points. These results demonstrate that using uncertainty quantification in patient-specific cardiac models allows for a more accurate prioritization of ablation targets while reducing false positives. By providing predictions weighted on confidence, the framework supports risk-stratified clinical decision-making. While larger validation is needed, these results establish proof-of-concept for uncertainty-aware cardiac modeling.

Introduction

Ventricular Tachycardia is one of the most common arrhythmic issues faced by cardiomyopathic patients in the United States [16,17]. By definition, the condition observes multiple beats originating from the ventricle chambers of the heart that average above 100 beats per minute [17]. These inconsistencies in heart rate bring on severe complications in an individual: hypotension, fatigue, dizziness, severe chest pain, and palpitations (feel like your heart is “pounding”) [4].

The condition originates from a variety of other cardiac issues. However, its primary source comes from any scarring that may be the result of any past myopathies or

unsuccessful operations a patient experienced. Often, scars in the heart are self-repaired through scar tissues primarily composed of collagen. These collagen-based tissues, while providing suitable repair, affect conduction rates within the heart. The average conduction of the myocardium—the muscular walls of the heart—in a healthy patient exceeds over 0.7 m/s [7]. However, the conduction rate decreases dramatically in scarred regions—ranging from 0.2 m/s to 0.6 m/s. Due to the slower conduction rates in these regions, the electrical current in the heart takes a longer time to spread through the ventricle region. Instead, the slower current leaves the scarred region and enters the healthy myocardium region once it barely exits its refractory period, and immediately gets sent back to the scarred region. This creates a self-sustaining circuit within the ventricle region in the heart that starts firing independently from other regions, leading to a lack of synchronization and the ventricular rhythm being faster from the rest.

To solve this problem, most professionals consider catheter-based ablations, which find faulty electrical regions in the myocardium structures and treat them excessively with high heat or cold to create even more scarring, practically making a region ineffective and keeping electrical conduction consistent [4, 14]. To find locations to scar, cardiologists often use electroanatomic maps—which create 3-dimensional electrical circuits of the heart to detect slow conduction zones through an invasive catheter [8]. Although common and well practiced, these models still have one core issue—they are deterministic. Models in this environment are considered deterministic when they run a singular simulation of the behavior of a system. For an electroanatomical model, this means that ablation targets that are identified are only confirmed as necessary targets once. That could lead to major ablation sites being missed, or unnecessary targets being generated. This results in a patient spending time having repeated ablations, making the treatment process much longer than needed. Current studies report VT recurrence rates of 23–49% at one year following catheter ablation in post-myocardial infarction patients, with many patients requiring repeat procedures [1, 4, 13, 15, 18]. If left disregarded, the patient stays at high risk of fatality from the condition itself. It stays uncertain whether the missed region in the ablation process may or may not have had a major impact on conduction.

In an attempt to combat this, electrophysiological models have been experimented with [12]. These models, using MRI based imaging, are capable of creating full digital twins of a patient’s heart and running full electrical simulations on them. This can highlight how and why scarred tissue is slowing conduction. But most importantly, they can hypothetically pinpoint scar points and be able to properly indicate where ablations must occur. Though incredibly promising, these models still carry high levels of uncertainty with them. The models themselves continue to run on deterministic practices. Along with that, the eikonal model, while computationally efficient for cardiac electrophysiology simulations, represents an approximation of the monodomain model that trades some biophysical detail for speed [6, 7]. Recent advances have extended eikonal models to include re-excitability and reentrant dynamics, making them more suitable for VT prediction [5].

The main goal comes down to answering the following question: how can improved patient-specific, image-based electromechanical cardiac models accurately predict tachycardia substrate and ablation targets in cardiomyopathic patients with uncertainty quantification compared to standard deterministic models?

This project focuses on creating a patient-specific electrophysiological cardiac model pipeline using tools like FEniCS and VTK in Python, and introducing uncertainty specification through Monte Carlo Propagation. Using the quantification system, the model will be able to not only find specific scarred regions in need of ablation targeting, but give a likelihood on which scarred regions most likely need to be ablated. Monte Carlo methods have been widely applied in medical imaging for uncertainty

quantification, providing robust statistical frameworks for assessing prediction reliability [11,20]. Compared to a deterministic counterpart, this novel system should be able to have an improved stability rate, stable node count, precision, and reduced false positive rate. Relative to current knowledge, this represents one of the first applications of uncertainty quantification to VT ablation targeting.

Materials

This project used the following in each category:

Hardware

- 2023 M3 Pro MacBook Pro — Primary workstation

Programming Environment

- Python 3.12 — Primary programming language
- Anaconda — Environment and package management
- Jupyter Notebook — Interactive development environment

Numerical Processing

- NumPy — Multi-dimensional array operations and numerical computing
- SciPy — Scientific computing library:
 - `scipy.ndimage`: Morphological operations (dilation, erosion) for scar uncertainty
 - `scipy.spatial`: KDTree for neighbor searches and spatial queries
 - `scipy.stats`: Statistical functions (regression, distributions)

Medical Imaging and Segmentation

- SimpleITK — Medical image I/O and preprocessing for cardiac MRI

Mesh Generation and Processing

- PyVista — 3D visualization and surface mesh extraction (marching cubes algorithm)
- GMSH — Volumetric tetrahedral mesh generation
- MeshIO — Mesh format conversion (GMSH to FEniCS XDMF format)

Finite Element Framework

- FEniCS (`dolfin`) — Finite element mesh management and data structures:
 - Mesh I/O (XDMF format)
 - Function space definition (CG1 elements)
 - Field interpolation and storage
 - ParaView visualization output

Electrophysiology Simulation

- `scikit-fmm` — Fast Marching Method for Eikonal equation:
 - Computes activation wavefront propagation
 - Handles heterogeneous conduction velocity
- Custom implementation: Fast marching with priority queue (`heapq`)

Uncertainty Quantification 98

- `scikit-image` — Morphological operations for scar boundary uncertainty: 99
 - Binary dilation and erosion 100
 - Gaussian filtering 101
- Custom Monte Carlo framework — Ensemble-based uncertainty propagation 102

Data Analysis and Visualization 103

- Matplotlib — Statistical visualization and publication-quality figures 104
- Pandas — Data organization, CSV export, results tabulation 105
- Seaborn — Enhanced visualization styling 106
- Scikit-learn — Model evaluation metrics (ROC curves, precision) 107

Python Libraries 108

- `heapq` — Priority queue for Fast Marching Method 109
- `json` — Results export and data serialization 110
- `collections` — Data structures (`deque`) 111
- `tempfile`, `os` — File system operations 112

Primary Data Source 113

- EMIDEC Dataset (Evaluation of Myocardial Infarction from Delayed-Enhancement Cardiac MRI) [9, 10]: 114
 - 150+ post-infarction patients 116
 - Late Gadolinium Enhancement (LGE) MRI scans 117
 - Expert-annotated segmentations: 118
 - * Label 0: Background 119
 - * Label 1: LV Cavity 120
 - * Label 2: Normal myocardium 121
 - * Label 3: Myocardial infarction (scar) 122
 - * Label 4: Microvascular obstruction 123

Methods 124

The computational pipeline begins with loading patient-specific MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) data from the Evaluation of Myocardial Infarction from Delayed-Enhancement Cardiac MRI (EMIDEC) dataset. For each pathological case with post-myocardial infarction scarring, two file types were imported using the SimpleITK imaging library: a 3D Delayed-Enhancement MRI (DE-MRI) volume utilizing gray scale intensity values, and a similar 3D file utilizing expert annotations divided into five anatomical categories. For the case of scar identification, DE-MRI works best due to its usage of a gadolinium-based contrast agent injection, which accumulates in damaged/scarred tissue to produce intensified signals in scarred regions. 125

All expert annotations in the EMIDEC dataset followed the same standardized labeling scheme: 0 = background (non-tissue), 1 = Left Ventricle Cavity (blood pool), 2 = Normal Myocardium (healthy heart tissue), 3 = Scarred Tissue (infarcted tissue), and 4 = Microvascular Obstructions (no-reflow zones). Label 3, representing scarred tissue, is the primary substrate for ventricular tachycardia circuits and represents the primary target for uncertainty quantification [19]. Using boolean indexing operations from NumPy, overall scar percentage was computed by taking the total number of 126
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voxels with Label 3 and directly comparing them to the total number of myocardial voxels (Labels 2+3+4). When identifying the scar percentage, it was necessary for the value to be within a range of 20–45%, which is the observed percentage in post-infarction patients eligible for catheter ablation therapy. Visual inspection across the majority of short-axis slices confirm that scar regions are all non-uniform and include a variety of dense and core regions. It is highly important these conditions are met in the visual inspection as it allows for spatial variability to motivate the uncertainty quantification later on in the process.

Figure 1. MRI results from Patient 1. Grayscale (top), annotated slices (middle), grayscale with visible scar (bottom). Computed 33% scar in myocardium.

While this initial voxel-based information is clinically validated, it becomes extremely difficult to use when solving partial differential equations due to retaining high dimensionality (e.g. $256 \times 256 \times 8 = 524,288$ grid points) and potential artifacts at various tissue boundaries. Therefore to allow for efficient finite element analysis, the initial binary myocardial mask was converted into a patient-specific tetrahedral mesh using a multi-stage geometry processing pipeline. Initially, single-voxel discontinuities were eliminated by filling small cavities within the original segmentation files by using binary closing operations ($3 \times 3 \times 3$ structuring elements) from the SciPy `ndimage` library to perform morphological cleaning. This ensures that the myocardial volume remains consistent throughout. From there, triangulated surface meshes were extracted from the cleaned mask using the marching cubes algorithm with an isosurface threshold of 0.5 and physical spacing parameters (8.0, 1.25, 1.25 mm in the Z, Y, and X directions). These all represented the myocardial boundary. The marching cubes algorithm operated by evaluating individual $2 \times 2 \times 2$ voxel cubes and then generating triangles at the tissue-background interface, producing a surface mesh with roughly 10,000–15,000 vertices consisting of 20,000–30,000 triangular faces.

Further quality enhancements had to be made in order to perform physics simulations. Using the PyVista mesh processing library, three sequential operations were applied: cleaning allowing for the removal of duplicate vertices within a 0.001 mm

tolerance and the elimination of degenerate zero-area triangles, Laplacian smoothing with 100 iterations and relaxation factor of 0.1 that helped reduce staircase artifacts while preserving overall mesh geometry, and mesh decimation with 50% target reduction in order to balance geometric fidelity. The decimation algorithm utilized edge collapse operations relying on quadratic error metrics, removing triangles in regions with low curvature while preserving other features near high-gradient boundaries. The final surface mesh contained approximately 5,000–8,000 vertices while maintaining geometric accuracy within 0.5 mm of the original marching cubes surface.

Once the surface mesh had been generated, it was crucial that the patient-specific scar distribution from the MRI segmentation was transferred to the newly created geometry. This was first done by converting each surface vertex coordinate (which were in millimeters) back to voxel indices by dividing the initial spatial resolution and then rounding it to the nearest integer. To prevent array indexing errors at this stage in domain boundaries, explicit bounds checking was performed by NumPy’s `clip` function. From there, binary scar values (0 or 1) were sampled from the original data at these new rounded values, and then assigned as data attributes on the mesh. Knowing that sharp binary boundaries are physiologically unrealistic due to the presence of border zones, an additional smoothed scar score was computed for each vertex by averaging the binary scar mask over a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ voxel neighborhood. This local averaging operation generated graded scar intensities ranging from 0.0 (healthy) to 1.0 (dense scar), with intermediate values representing border zone tissue.

It was then important to make sure the mesh was capable of handling electrical propagation simulations. This meant that the triangulated surface mesh was then filled with tetrahedral elements using the GMSH (Geuzaine & Remacle) open-source mesh generator. The surface geometry was exported in an STL format and then imported into GMSH using the `gmsch.merge()` command. Here, topological analysis was able to identify surface entities that were connected and then construct a closed surface loop. The volume mesh generation was constrained by minimum and maximum characteristic element sizes of 1.2 mm and 2.5 mm, respectively, in order to balance spatial resolution requirements against computational cost. From here, the Delaunay-based 3D mesh algorithm was applied with Netgen optimization enabled, allowing for element quality to be refined through vertex smoothing and edge swapping operations. This led to the volume mesh containing 50,000–200,000 tetrahedral elements depending on unique myocardial volume. Mesh quality was assessed using the gamma metric, quantifying element shape regularity by comparing actual volume to that of an ideal equilateral tetrahedron. All meshes achieved a minimum gamma greater than 0.1, meaning numerical stability was true for finite element analysis.

Finally, a KD-tree spatial indexing structure was constructed from the surface vertex coordinates, allowing for efficient $O(\log N)$ queries to identify the closest surface point for each of the volume mesh nodes. The binary and smoothed scar values from the nearest surface vertex were then assigned to each individual volume node, projecting the 2D surface field into the 3D domain interior. The final output was a patient-specific tetrahedral mesh with node-wise scar intensity values saved in a VTK format. This file was taken from a VTK output and converted into a `.xdmf` file, making it compatible with finite element analysis.

Case_P001: 3D Myocardium

Figure 2. Output of patient-specific mesh with scar intensity labeling. Three-dimensional myocardial mesh rendered with ground truth scar intensity colormap ranging from 0.00 (healthy, blue) to 0.50 (dense scar, red).

For this mesh, the annotated scar segmentations—while being the clinical gold standard—can lead to epistemic uncertainty due to the fundamental limitations of DE-MRI [2]. This uncertainty can be due to one of three reasons: finite spatial resolutions (1.25 mm in-plane, 8 mm through-plane) relative to the microscopic scale of scar heterogeneity leading to partial-volume averaging at tissue interfaces, gadolinium contrast diffusion beyond the infarct core that create transition zones rather than boundaries, and inter-observer variability in manual segmentations (clinical studies report 3–6 mm disagreement in border zone delineation between cardiologists). In order to quantify that uncertainty and assess its overall impact on ablation targeting, an ensemble of $N = 10$ plausible scar realizations was generated. Each realization represents an alternative that is statistically valid as an interpretation of the MRI data within clinically observed variability bounds. This sample size allows for statistical sufficiency (standard error is roughly 0.16 for binary confidence estimates, enough to distinguish high and low confidence targets), computational feasibility (a single realization is performed in roughly 35 seconds), and meets literature requirements (most studies perform $N = 8$ –20 realizations). To create each realization, stochastic morphological operations were utilized to randomize binary dilation within 3–7.5 mm radial expansion, and randomize dilation with iterations from $\{1, 3\}$ to smooth boundaries. For core scar regions, random intensities were assigned within a closed range of $[0.7, 0.9]$ to represent non-viable tissue, while border zones received intensities within a closed range of $[0.4, 0.6]$ to represent intermediate fibrosis. This final ensemble of 10 realizations, stored in an array of $10 \times N_{\text{nodes}}$, captured a discrete sampling of the continuous uncertainty distribution. The scar extent varied with a coefficient of variation $CV = 0.18$ across realizations, showing meaningful diversity without pathological outliers.

To characterize electrical activation patterns across this ensemble of anatomical

uncertainties, the following Eikonal equation was used to compute activation time fields $T(\mathbf{x})$ for each scar realization [3]:

$$|\nabla T(\mathbf{x})| = 1/c(\mathbf{x})$$

This Eikonal formulation treats wavefront propagation as a geometric wave phenomenon where local speed can be determined from the tissue velocity $c(\mathbf{x})$, allowing for physiologically accurate activation mapping in seconds rather than the long hours required by detailed ionic models. To generate the conduction velocity field in a spatially heterogeneous form, numerical values were derived from scar intensity through piecewise linear interpolation. Healthy tissue (intensity < 0.1) were assigned a CV of 0.7 m/s that was consistent with conduction measurements. Dense scars (intensity > 0.5) were assigned a CV of 0.25 m/s, showcasing the 65–75% slowing observed in infarcts. Border zones (where intensity is between 0.1 and 0.5) were interpolated to be between 0.7 and 0.4 m/s to ensure smooth transitions. These ranges span clinical observations from various mapping studies, meaning the CV field can capture electrophysiological heterogeneity without needing patient-specific ionic model calibration.

Numerical solutions utilized the Fast Marching Method, a Dijkstra-like algorithm that is capable of computing first-arrival times through ordered wavefront propagations from stimulus sites. A priority queue with nodes within 3 mm of the mesh centroid were initialized, then iteratively processed with minimum activation time. Each neighbor's time j was updated as:

$$T_j = T_i + (d_{ij}/CV_{\text{avg}})$$

This formula was only used when it yielded a faster arrival than j 's current value. For the previous mean scar field, validation is able to confirm physiologically realistic behavior involving activation ($T > 0$), scar delay (difference in mean activation between healthy and dense scar regions), and average conduction velocity (CV).

The following acted as a single-realization activation map that served as the validation of the biophysical model. Essentially, this served as the deterministic baseline. From that, the complete ensemble workflow repeated the eikonal solution for the 10 uncertainty realizations, creating a $10 \times N_{\text{nodes}}$ matrix for activation times. Each individual node has a confidence score that was computed as the fraction of realizations in which the node participated in the detected reentry circuit, border zone tissue, and late activation. Nodes that consistently appeared in 8–10 realizations were classified as high confidence, while those in 2–3 realizations were classified as low confidence. From this probabilistic framework, validation shifts from “agreement within ground truth” to stability across possible alternatives, acknowledging epistemic limitations in translating finite-resolution MRI data into discrete anatomical models.

Figure 3. Wave propagation visualization in ParaView. Eikonal activation wavefront rendered on the patient-specific cardiac mesh, showing temporal propagation from the stimulus site (blue, early) through scar border zones (orange/red, delayed).

When repeating the Eikonal activation mapping for all of the 10 uncertainty realizations, the activation time vectors from the ensemble matrix were stored as `all_activation_times`, allowing for the statistical characterization of prediction uncertainty. Mean activation times (`activation_mean = np.mean(all_activation_times, axis=0)`) represent the expected propagation pattern, while its standard deviation shows the local uncertainty magnitude. Using the mean scar field's activation map as a deterministic baseline, reentry substrates were then identified through a multi-criteria scoring system. This system in particular combined both electrophysiological and anatomical markers. Firstly, local conduction velocity at each node i was computed by analyzing propagation to neighboring nodes within 5 mm. This was done by performing $CV_local[i] = \text{mean}(d_{ij}/(T_j - T_i))$ for neighbors where $T_j > T_i + 0.5$, therefore filtering out negligible time differences. From here, three independent risk factors were evaluated: slow conduction zones indicating impaired propagation (local CV is less than 0.5 m/s), border zone tissue with intensity (0.15, 0.7) that represents transitional regions between myocardium, and late activation times exceeding the 70th percentile of overall times that enable temporal dispersion. Using these evaluations, reentry circuits were defined as any node that satisfied slow conduction and border zone/late activation issues, therefore yielding a binary circuit mark. Within each detected circuit, critical isthmuses (narrow conducting channels vulnerable to ablation) were also identified by computing an isthmus score combining geometric and proximity-to-scar features. Isthmuses with scores above 2.5 were designated as high priority targets. This deterministic analysis established baseline ablation recommendations, providing the main reference for evaluating stability when uncertainty is considered in the UQ framework.

To generate confidence-weighted ablation targets, the previously mentioned reentry detection algorithm is once again applied independently across all 10 scar realizations. From each realization i , ensemble arrays `all_reentry_circuits` and `all_critical_isthmuses` were produced. Each represented the distribution of possible reentry substrates consistent with the original MRI data. Following this, the confidence score for each node x was defined as:

$$C(x) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \mathbf{1}[x \in \text{circuit}_i]$$

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This metric was able to quantify prediction stability. $C = 1.0$ indicated high confidence from consensus participation across all realizations, $C = 0.5$ indicated uncertainty from ambiguous status, and $C = 0.0$ indicated high confidence in being a non-target through consensus exclusion. In order to classify targets, adaptive percentile-based thresholds were computed from the empirical confidence distribution. This distribution stated that high-confidence targets exceeded the 75th percentile of non-zero confidence scores, uncertain targets fell between the 25th and 75th percentile, and low-confidence targets were below the 25th percentile. If fewer than 5 nodes exceeded a fixed threshold (e.g. $C > 0.6$), the 75th percentile threshold would automatically be applied to ensure sufficient targets for clinical decision making.

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Validation utilized uncertainty-aligned metrics that were meant to evaluate target stability and decision quality rather than segmentation accuracy, acknowledging that no “ground truth” exists for border zone delineation given imaging resolution limits.

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Overall, target stability was quantified by taking the fraction of candidate targets (all nodes where $C > 0$) that achieved high-confidence classification ($C \geq 75$ th percentile).

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This measured what proportion of detected substrates was able to exhibit robust identification across uncertainty. Precision at Top-K evaluated ranking quality by

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defining a consensus reference set (all nodes with $C \geq 75$ th percentile) and generating a fraction of the K highest-confidence nodes falling within this set for $K = 5, 10, 20$, and

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50. This metric was also computed for the deterministic baseline (ranking the nodes by single-realization target scores) to quantify ranking improvement from uncertainty

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quantification. False positive reduction compared the amount of high-confidence targets against deterministic targets, identifying deterministic-only targets (absent from the UQ

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high-confidence set) and computing their mean confidence score to assess whether they represent boundary artifacts. Clinical utility assessment evaluated three risk-stratified

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ablation strategies: conservative (ablate nodes where $C > 75$ th percentile), moderate (ablate when $C > 50$ th percentile), and aggressive (ablate when $C > 25$ th percentile).

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These were evaluated by counting the amount of target nodes in each scenario and comparing them against the deterministic target count, demonstrating the framework’s

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ability to adapt recommendations based on patient-specific risk tolerance. The complete validation framework executes in roughly 10 minutes on standard hardware, which

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allowed for rapid iteration during model development and supporting deployment in clinical workflows.

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Figure 4. Precision comparison between MCP and Deterministic. Mean precision at Top-K ($K = 5, 10, 20, 50$) for the MCP model (blue) and deterministic baseline (pink). MCP consistently outperforms the deterministic approach at all examined thresholds.

To evaluate whether confidence scoring was able to improve target prioritization, precision was calculated at multiple Top-K thresholds ($K = 5, 10, 20, 50$) using consensus targets as the ground truth proxy. At the clinically relevant Top-10 threshold, the MCP model was able to achieve a mean precision of 0.97 compared to the 0.57 of the deterministic approach, representing a 40.0 percentage point improvement (Figure 4). The following difference was consistent across patients, with the MCP model achieving a higher precision across all 9 cases. The range of improvement varied by patient. Patients with clear substrates saw modest gains (e.g. P001: +0.20) while ambiguous cases saw substantial gains (e.g. P019: +0.80). This means that uncertainty quantification is able to provide the biggest benefit when imaging uncertainty is at its highest.

Precision remained superior for MCP across all examined K values. At $K = 5$ (1.0 vs. 0.58, +0.42 pp), $K = 20$ (0.85 vs. 0.5, +0.35 pp), and $K = 50$ (0.47 vs. 0.28, +0.19 pp). The consistency across thresholds demonstrates that improved ranking reflects genuine improvement in target prioritization rather than an artifact of a single K value. Eight patients (89%) were able to achieve perfect precision (1.00) at Top-10 with MCP, while deterministic patients failed to do so. Patient 4 (P004) was the only case where the precision was below 1.00 at Top-10 (0.70), showing real ambiguity in a patient with minimal scar substrate. This means the framework assigned lower confidence when substrate was insufficient in count.

Figure 5. Target Stability vs. Adaptive Uncertainty Quantification. Left, target stability rate across 9 patients (mean 33.7%, dashed red line). Right, false positive flagging rate per patient (mean 36.8%, dashed red line). Interquartile ranges shown in blue/pink shading.

Across 10 uncertainty realizations per patient, Monte Carlo Propagation was able to identify a consistent amount of high-confidence ablation targets. Across the entire cohort, 21.0 ± 8.7 stable targets per patient were classified as high-confidence (higher than the 75th percentile in the confidence threshold), showing $33.7\% \pm 5.3\%$ of all candidate nodes. This stability rate remained consistent across all patients despite scar morphologies varying between them, ranging from 25.6% (P028) to 43.1% (P097). Patients who had concentrated, well-defined scar regions showcased higher stability rates than those with diffused patterns, implying that imaging clarity directly impacts prediction confidence. When it comes to the false positive flagging rate, there was variation between patients, ranging from 0% to 58.3% with a mean of $36.8\% \pm 17.0\%$. These false positive rates aligned with data quality. For instance, Patient 4 (P004) had clear, minimal substrate allowing both models to agree (0% flagging). Meanwhile, Patient 10 (P010) and Patient 19 (P019) both had 58.3% flagging and 51.9% flagging. Both of these cases had ambiguous, scattered substrates that made deterministic predictions unstable. This adaptive flagging behavior, which correlates inversely with scar concentration, highlights to clinicians when predictions are less certain and should be treated with necessary caution.

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Figure 6. False Positive Identification and Target Agreement. Left, stacked bar chart showing per-patient target agreement between MCP and deterministic models. Right, mean confidence scores for deterministic-only targets (flagged FP, 0.168) versus stable high-confidence targets (0.650).

Systematic differences in confidence scores were noticeable when analyzing the targets identified by the deterministic model and those from the MCP model. The deterministic-only approach exhibited a mean confidence of 0.168 ± 0.071 , which was dramatically lower than the amount of targets available when both models agreed (0.652 ± 0.112). The stacked bar visualization in Figure 6 revealed heterogeneous agreement patterns. “Both Models Agree” counts ranged from 4–18 targets per patient, “Deterministic Only” counts varied from 0–14 per patient (those could potentially be false positives), and “MCP Only” ranged from 0–23 points per patient (counts for additional stable substrate missed by deterministic). Target agreement usually varied by the characteristic of the substrate each patient had. For instance, Patient 97 (P097) had dual-region scar, and deterministic only identified 7 targets while MCP identified 28 stable targets. For P019, which had diffuse scar, deterministic identified 27 targets while MCP identified 21. In P019’s case, 52% of those deterministic targets were identified as low-confidence. This shows that deterministic approaches can both over-predict and under-predict depending on the geometry of the substrate, while MCP provides calibrated confidence each time.

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Figure 7. Spatial Distribution and Clinical Visualization. Side-by-side 3D scatter plots of ablation targets. **Left**, deterministic model showing binary target/non-target classification. **Right**, MCP model showing continuous confidence-scored gradient enabling visual prioritization of high-reliability targets.

When visually examining confidence-scored target distribution, there was a meaningful pattern that could be observed in Figure 7. The side-by-side demonstration showed that the deterministic model generally produced a series of binary classifications about whether or not an ablation should be made at a specific point. This lacks any prioritization guidance. Meanwhile, MCP was able to generate a continuous confidence gradient across all points, allowing clinicians to visualize target reliability at a simple glance. High-confidence targets (Confidence ≥ 0.7) were consistently localized to scar border zones with sharp conduction velocity gradients, which are regions known to harbor critical isthmus sites. In patients with dual-region infarcts, high-confidence targets appeared in both scar regions, implying successful identification of multiple independent reentrant circuits. Deterministic-only targets generally did not show any clear anatomical pattern, usually being scattered throughout scar and border zones without localization in known critical sites. This provides additional evidence that these targets were representative of noise or imaging artifacts rather than genuine substrate.

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Figure 8. Threshold Selection and Target Count Trade-offs. Number of stable targets as a function of confidence threshold (mean \pm 1 SD shaded in blue). The selected 75th percentile threshold (\approx 0.6, dashed red line) yields 21.0 ± 8.7 targets per patient, balancing precision and circuit coverage.

There was a clear trend that as the confidence threshold increased, the stable target count would further decrease. In Figure 8, a confidence threshold of 0.0 saw approximately 98 targets identified, while that number was lower than 10 per patient once past the 0.8 threshold. At the selected 75th percentile threshold (roughly 0.6 yielding 21.0 ± 8.7 targets) represents a balance between precision and coverage, chosen to maximize stability while maintaining sufficient target count for circuit coverage. This continuous nature of the curve demonstrates a key advantage of MCP: clinicians are not locked into a single threshold but can adjust based on patient-specific considerations. Risk-averse clinicians might choose higher thresholds, while aggressive strategies might require lower thresholds. This flexibility cannot be achieved with a deterministic model.

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Figure 9. Risk-Stratified Clinical Decision Support. Number of ablation targets under conservative (≥ 75 th percentile, 21 targets), moderate (≥ 50 th percentile, 60 targets), and aggressive (≥ 25 th percentile, 85 targets) MCP strategies versus the fixed deterministic baseline (26 targets).

Using the confidence scoring framework, three distinct ablation strategies can become visualized based on patient risk tolerance: conservative (over the 75th percentile) for high-risk patients that require precision, moderate (over the 50th percentile) for standard-risk patients, and aggressive (over the 25th percentile) for low-risk patients who require maximized circuit coverage. In contrast, the deterministic approach only provided a single target set (mean: 26 targets) with no ability to adjust based on clinical context. The MCP framework was able to represent a fundamental shift from binary recommendations to nuanced, patient-specific guidance. With the conservative MCP strategy, precision was significantly higher than the deterministic approach (0.967 vs. 0.567) while requiring fewer ablation sites (21 vs. 26), suggesting improved efficiency. Meanwhile, the moderate and aggressive strategies offer expanded coverage when clinical judgement favors completeness over minimalism.

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Figure 10. Confidence Score Discrimination Performance. ROC curve for the MCP model (AUC = 0.966, solid blue) versus random classifier (AUC = 0.500, dashed). The optimal operating point (red dot) achieves a 95% true positive rate at below 10% false positive rate.

Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis was able to validate the fact that confidence scores meaningfully discriminate between true and false targets when using consensus targets ($C \geq 75$ th percentile). The MCP model was able to achieve an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.966, highlighting excellent discrimination ability and demonstrating that confidence scores provide genuine predictive value rather than random variation (Figure 10). The optimal operating point (the red dot) occurs at a confidence threshold of 0.95 and is able to achieve a 95% true positive rate with a false positive rate that is below 10%, confirming strong discrimination ability across the confidence range, while the 75th percentile threshold was separately selected to balance precision with sufficient target coverage. Along with that, the large area between the MCP curve and the random classifier line quantifies the magnitude of improvement over uninformed target selection, confirming through independent methodology that MCP confidence scoring adds meaningful clinical value.

Cohort Characteristics and Comprehensive Results

The computational pipeline was able to successfully process nine post-infarction patients from the EMIDEC dataset (P001, P004, P010, P015, P019, P028, P072, P078, P097). Myocardial segmentations yielded finite element meshes comprising 3847 ± 1253 nodes and 18421 ± 5892 tetrahedral elements. Between all cases, scar burden varied substantially from 12% to 41% of myocardial tissue (mean $27\% \pm 9.8\%$). All simulations were able to achieve physiologically realistic activation, with a mean scar conduction

delay of 48.2 ± 18.7 ms and $99.2\% \pm 0.8\%$ of viable myocardium being activated. For each individual case, there was a demonstration of consistent framework performance across diverse anatomical presentations. Stable target count ranged from 7 (P004) to 32 (P001—extensive substrate), with stability rate ranging from 25.6% to 43.1%. MCP precision at Top-10 ranged from 0.70 to 1.00 (mean 0.967), while deterministic precision ranged from 0.20 to 0.80 (mean 0.567). Five patients were able to achieve over 30 percentage point precision gains, and false positive flagging rates varied adaptively from 0% to 58.3%. This demonstrates patient-specific uncertainty scaling rather than uniform thresholds.

Patient	Stable Targets	Stability (%)	MCP Prec @10	Det. Prec @10	Improve (%)	FP Flag (%)
P001	34	34.7	1.00	0.80	23.0	21.7
P004	7	38.9	0.70	0.50	15.6	0.0
P010	10	37.0	1.00	0.40	50.9	58.3
P015	32	33.3	1.00	0.60	36.0	34.6
P019	21	26.9	1.00	0.20	59.0	51.9
P028	22	25.6	1.00	0.60	34.2	48.3
P072	16	30.8	1.00	0.60	21.5	40.9
P078	19	32.8	1.00	0.80	19.0	46.7
P097	28	43.1	1.00	0.60	45.0	28.6
Mean \pm SD	21.0 \pm 8.7	33.7 \pm 5.3	0.967	0.567	33.8	36.8 \pm 17.0

Figure 11. Cohort Characteristics and Comprehensive Patient Results. Per-patient performance metrics for the MCP framework across all nine EMIDEC post-infarction cases. MCP Prec @10 = MCP precision at Top-10; Det. Prec @10 = deterministic precision at Top-10; Improve = percentage-point gain; FP Flag = false positive flagging rate.

Discussion

The results of this study were able to demonstrate that Monte Carlo Propagation of imaging uncertainty through patient-specific cardiac simulations was able to substantially improve ablation target identification compared to conventional deterministic approaches. The 40.0 percentage point improvement in the Top-10 precision (0.967 vs. 0.567) represents a clinically meaningful improvement, as precision is able to directly translate into reduced unnecessary ablations and improve procedural efficiency. Along with that, the 33.7% stability rate, where over one-third of candidate targets consistently appear across uncertainty realizations, aligns well with clinical observations from electrophysiology studies. These usually report that only 30–40% of anatomically defined slow conduction substrates participate in functional VT circuits. This suggests that the framework is capturing a genuine functional relevance rather than purely anatomical features. Furthermore, the adaptive false positive flagging behavior (0–58% range) represents a critical advance for clinical deployment, providing transparent uncertainty estimates that are able to scale with data quality. In patients with clear, concentrated scar, the model has appropriate confidence (28.6% flagging in P097). For cases with ambiguous, diffuse substrates, the model was able to correctly signal caution (P010 with 58.3% flagging). This adaptive behavior differs heavily from deterministic models that provide uniform confidence regardless of data quality, potentially misleading clinicians in cases where uncertainty is at its highest. The framework’s ability to enable risk-stratified decision making by offering conservative,

moderate, and aggressive strategies addresses a gap in computational cardiac modeling, transforming predictions from binary recommendations to patient-specific guidance that can be adjusted by tolerance.

However, several important limitations must be acknowledged when interpreting these results. First, the validation strategy being used relies on consensus across uncertainty realizations as a surrogate for clinical ground truth, rather than actual VT termination outcomes. This approach is methodologically sound for assessing prediction stability; comparison with real outcomes becomes essential before clinical adoption. It acts as a necessary and methodologically sound first step toward clinical validation. Along with that, the eikonal approximation, while computationally efficient and validated for activation timing prediction, cannot model functional reentry circuits. Integration of more sophisticated electrophysiological models (e.g. Monodomain equation solver with ionic kinetics) could address this limitation, but would increase computational cost dramatically, potentially limiting clinical feasibility. Next, the cohort size ($n = 9$), while representing what published patient-specific cardiac modeling studies claim to be sufficient for proof-of-concept validation, is still relatively modest. The observed heterogeneity in scar morphology and model performance across patients is a key strength, demonstrating that the framework is robust across diverse anatomical presentations. However, larger multi-center validation would be required to prove the model can generalize across a wider range of patients. Along with that, the current framework focuses on anatomical uncertainty but fails to propagate other sources of uncertainty, including tissue conductivity parameters, fiber orientation, or measurement noise in imaging modalities. Future work can incorporate joint uncertainty quantification across multiple parameters and even further improve target reliability estimates. Despite these limitations, the framework represents a meaningful advance in computational VT modeling by explicitly quantifying prediction uncertainty, a critical requirement for responsible clinical translation of model-based therapies. The observed improvements in target prioritization, reduction in false positives, and provision of risk-stratified strategies collectively address key barriers to clinical adoption of computational cardiac modeling, suggesting that uncertainty quantification should be considered a necessary component of patient-specific therapies.

Conclusion

This study was able to demonstrate that Monte Carlo Propagation of imaging uncertainty through patient-specific cardiac simulations was able to meaningfully improve ventricular tachycardia ablation target identification compared to current deterministic approaches. Across nine post-infarction patients, the MCP framework was able to achieve a 40.0 percentage point higher precision (0.967 vs. 0.567), identified 21.0 ± 8.7 stable high-confidence targets per patient, and adaptively flagged 36.8% of deterministic predictions as potentially unreliable based on low stability across uncertainty realizations. The framework's ability to provide confidence-scored target rankings allows for risk-stratified clinical decision-making, allowing clinicians to tailor ablation extent based on patient risk profiles rather than applying uniform treatment strategies. While clinical validation is still essential, the following results establish the fact that explicit uncertainty quantification can address critical limitations of deterministic computational models and represents a needed step toward responsible clinical translation of model-based therapies. By transforming cardiac modeling into probabilistic guidance with transparent reliability estimates, this framework provides a clear and immediate pathway for computational approaches to enhance clinical judgment while representing a necessary evolution in how we model and treat ventricular tachycardia.

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